

Brigada Eskwela's Level of Execution in Kinangan Integrated School

JESSA C. ALCASIN

Master of Arts in Education Major in School Administration and Supervision, East West Mindanao Colleges INC.
Kamasi, Ampatuan, Maguindanao

Teacher, Division of Davao Occidental, Department of Education, Philippines, 8011

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Abstract: The objective of my study would be to evaluate the execution of Brigada Eskwela implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Malita South District, Division of Davao Occidental for the School Year 2020-2021. Experiential pieces of evidence revealed that year after year, the Department of Education had been implementing several projects, activities, and programs that helped realize sound philosophical and legal frameworks of the department which includes Brigada Eskwela among others. Thus, my mixed quantitative-qualitative study unveiled the experiences of the teachers and school head of Kinangan Integrated School using the purposive sampling technique. The results revealed that the best practices in Brigada implementation are in marketing strategy and advocacy of the implementation, in the conduct of the stakeholders' forum, and in adding flavor to the bayanihan. The overall rating of the level of Brigada Eskwela implementation is 4.5, described as "Very High". This is found significant to a small-sized school as well as to the perception of the school head, teachers, PTA Officials.

Keywords: brigada eskwela, school volunteerism, teachers, school heads, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Careful preparation for the initial class is imperative for every school. Preparation and attitude are transmittable and generally, students will pick up the enthusiasm, be more likely to compel to the class, and capitalize greater energy in the class. Concerning this, school administrators and faculty members ensure that the opening of classes has to be the most exciting part of every student's school life.

Preparing high schools for college attainment, for instance, is a great deal in the United States of America. The former US President, Barack Obama (2014) said that it is this generation's task to reignite the true engine of America's economic growth—a rising, thriving middle class. Reigniting that engine depends on education, preschool through grade 12 and beyond, strong enough to prepare all students for college, careers, and the innovation-based economy in which they will make their living (US Department of Education, 2011).

Over the years in the Philippines, the *Brigada Eskwela* effort in most schools has evolved from a week-long cleaning-up and beautification exercise to a festive coming together of stakeholders in education: students, teachers, school officials, parents, civil society, local government officials, religious groups, and the private sector. The Department of Education launched National Schools Maintenance Week to bring the spirit of volunteerism to the community level, maximize civil participation and utilize local resources to improve public schools. Every year, various stakeholders unite and work together to repair and prepare public schools for the opening of classes.

Former DepEd Secretary Br. Armin Luistro FSC said that there is no other country that prepares for school opening the way the Philippines does. It's only in the Philippines where close to seven million Filipinos volunteer to help clean schools. As the Department of Education endeavors to solve many other challenges plaguing Philippine education, there is *Brigada*

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Eskwela that reminds everyone that when Filipinos unite, a better future will be built together in the hope of bringing in quality education (Department of Education).

According to DepEd Memorandum No. 43, s. 2017, entitled “2017 *Brigada Eskwela* Implementing Guidelines”, the implementation of the *Brigada Eskwela* shall be evaluated based on the scope of work, diverse volunteer participation, general resource, alignment to *Brigada Eskwela* theme, creativity and innovation, and increment of resources and volunteers.

It is here that accountability sets in, the obligation of an individual or organization to account for its activities, accept responsibility for them, and transparently disclose the results. It also includes the responsibility for money or other entrusted property which is prevalent in many *Brigada Eskwela* best practices.

Year after year, the Department of Education has been implementing several projects, activities, and programs (PAPs) that realize the sound philosophical and legal frameworks of the department. These PAPs include *Brigada Eskwela* among others.

In its fourth year of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation, the Division of Davao Occidental, Region XI has been observed that although the schools are doing their best in linking with the different school stakeholders, inadequate results had been reported by schools in this particular endeavor. Hence, this study is proposed to investigate the level of execution of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation in Kinangan Integrated School.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

To evaluate the execution of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental for the School Year 2020-2021 was the main objective of this study. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the level of execution of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation in terms of:
 - 1.1 organization of *Brigada Eskwela* committee;
 - 1.2 marketing strategies and advocacies;
 - 1.3 resource mobilization;
 - 1.4 program implementation; and
 - 1.5 monitoring and evaluation.
2. Determine the best practices in the execution of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Level of Execution of *Brigada Eskwela* Implementation

Table I. Level of Execution of *Brigada Eskwela* Implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental

PARTICULAR	MODE	DESCRIPTION
A. Organization of <i>Brigada Eskwela</i> Committee	4	High
B. Marketing Strategies and Advocacies	5	Very High
C. Resource Mobilization	5	Very High
D. Program Implementation	5	Very High
E. Monitoring and Evaluation	4	High

Table 1 shows the level of execution *Brigada Eskwela* implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental. Of the five stages of *Brigada Eskwela* implementation two items, the Organization of *Brigada Eskwela* Committee and Monitoring and Evaluation are rated 4 which description is “high”. The other three stages: Marketing

Strategies and Advocacies, Resource Mobilization, and Program Implementation are rated 5 which description is “Very High”. These imply that the execution of the *Brigada Eskwela* implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental was already in place and in full swing of its implementation.

Gamil & Melican (2015) declares that we hear news about the shortage of classrooms, overcrowded classes, and schools were not ready for the upcoming school year, year after year. DepEd addressed this issue through the Adopt-a-School Program. This initiative allowed a partnership with other stakeholders who are willing to share resources to improve the country's public-school education. In a few years, the spirit of volunteerism reached partners and generated programs and interventions.

Carreon (2015) states that the collaborative effort of school heads, private partners, local government units, and community members, including parents and students, lies the success of its implementation. Through the initiative of the school heads, private partners are allowed to contribute resources to the effort. And in honor of their goodwill, private partners are offered tax incentives of up to 150%. Local government units and community members mostly provide workforce and volunteer services during this weeklong activity.

The Best Practices in the Execution of *Brigada Eskwela*

Table 2 shows the themes and core ideas on the best practices of Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental. These themes and core ideas were produced and established from the responses in the conduct of the Key Informant Interview (KII).

Table II. Themes and Core Ideas on the Best Practices of Kinangan Integrated School in the Execution of *Brigada Eskwela*

Themes	Core Ideas (Practices)
1. Marketing Strategy and Advocacy of the Implementation	Information dissemination through caravan to encourage attendance of volunteers and advance resource mobilization.
	Information dissemination through broadcasting to encourage attendance of volunteers and advance resource mobilization.
	Information dissemination through the hanging of tarpaulin to encourage attendance of volunteers and advance resource mobilization.
2. Conduct of the Stakeholders' Forum	Establishment of community linkages for partnership.
	Organization of workforce through creating committees.
	The Institution of the division of labor in the spirit of <i>bayanihan</i>
3. Additional Flavor to the <i>Bayanihan</i>	Employing creativity in the conduct of the <i>bayanihan</i> for fun like initiating raffle draws parlor games, short programs, and giving of awards to volunteers.
	Substantiate the conduct of the <i>bayanihan</i> by employing fire, earthquake, and typhoon drills.
	Deliver services like free medical services, haircuts for learners, and school supplies.

The themes of the best practices in the implementation of *Brigada Eskwela* which arise from the investigation of the responses of the respondents are the following: Marketing Strategy and Advocacy of the Implementation, Conduct of the Stakeholders' Forum, and Additional Flavor to the Conduct of the *Bayanihan*.

In the theme, Marketing Strategy and Advocacy of the Implementation, the core ideas surfaced are: First, Information dissemination through caravan to inspire attendance of volunteers and develop resource mobilization. Second, Information dissemination through broadcasting inspires the attendance of volunteers and advanced resource mobilization. Third, Information dissemination through the hanging of tarpaulin to reassure attendance of volunteers and advance resource

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mobilization. These suggest that these practices have already been the culture of the school during the implementation of the *Bayanihan sa Paaralan* better known as *Brigada Eskwela*.

Adams and Christenson (2007) claimed that there is a need to create linkages with the community to make the most of the effectiveness of services of the schools. In the *Brigada Eskwela Manual for School Heads* (2009), the Department of Education supposed that effective implementation of the program needs the involvement of the majority of community members and school stakeholders.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study of the level of execution of Brigada Eskwela implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental has drawn the following conclusions based on the findings obtained:

The implementation of Brigada Eskwela was already in place and in the full swing of its implementation in Kinangan Integrated School, Division of Davao Occidental.

For the best practices in the execution of the Brigada Eskwela implementation, the marketing strategy and advocacy was characterized by information dissemination through the caravan, broadcasting, and hanging of tarpaulin to encourage attendance of volunteers and advance resource mobilization. While, the conduct of the stakeholders' forum, was characterized by the establishment of community linkages for partnership, the organization of workforce through creating committees, and the institution of the division of labor in the spirit of bayanihan. Finally, the additional flavor to the bayanihan was characterized by employing creativity in the conduct of the bayanihan for fun like initiating raffle draws, parlor games, short programs, and giving of awards to volunteers; substantiating the conduct of the bayanihan by employing fire, earthquake and typhoon drills; and delivering services like free medical services, haircut for learners, and school supplies.

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